

Revision of *Stagmomantis* Saussure, 1869

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Stagmomantis is currently an aggregate of morphologically diverse species that have been historically grouped into various taxonomic subdivisions based upon their shared characteristics. In 1917, Giglio-Tos organized a set of species subdivisions as separate genera apart from *Stagmomantis* and used basic morphological characters to delineate the differences between them. Four years later, in 1922, Hebard rejected Giglio-Tos' segregation of *Stagmomantis* into separate genera and synonymized these subdivisions, stating that they "have at best no higher than group value within the genus." In 1935, Rehn further criticized Giglio-Tos' simplistic criteria for the demarcation of his proposed genera and offered instead his own ordering of species subdivisions into defined groups. Rehn's group concept of the species subdivisions was constructed through a much more thorough and sophisticated analysis than that of Giglio-Tos but he essentially reached the same conclusions as the former author, as Rehn's species groups demonstrated clear parallels to the generic divisions that were first introduced by Giglio-Tos'.

Without a proper phylogenetic study to map out the exact relationships between the various species of *Stagmomantis*, the taxonomic ranking of the species subdivisions that were created by Giglio-Tos and Rehn remain open to interpretation. To help clarify this problem, Rodrigues initiated a phylogenetic study of Mantidae in 2018. Although the final results of this study remain pending, Rodrigues reported through personal correspondence with the present author that his preliminary data regarding the members of *Stagmomantis* "indicate that the genus needs to be split as there are different lineages grouped together." At present, there is only enough data to confidently segregate *Isomantis* away from the other species clusters and reinstate this monotypic division as its own genus. Several of the remaining subdivisions will also most likely need to be returned to genus status at some point in the near future for reasons similar to those that warrant the separation of *Isomantis*. But until further studies can compellingly challenge Rehn's organization of species within *Stagmomantis*, the subdivisions that have been constructed by him should remain in place within this taxon. However, as both Giglio-Tos and Rehn reached roughly the same conclusions through different methodologies regarding the segregation of the various species within *Stagmomantis*, it is clear that the subdivisions erected by these two authors have merit and thus should be regarded with an

elevated taxonomic designation of subgenera rather than the informal group designation as proposed by Rehn.

Stagmomantis Saussure, 1869

Description. Habitus measuring 35.5-74 mm. Significant sexual dimorphism present. Habitus of male slender and moderately elongated, that of female generally much more stout, robust. Head capsule triangular, wider than tall. Compound eyes slightly protruding, prominent, rounded. Ocelli small in female, large in male. Antennae filiform, reaching to base of pronotum in male, much shorter in female. Lower frons distinctively transverse, broad, always more than twice as wide as high, slightly curved in middle of superior margin. Vertex bearing 4 sulci, nearly straight or weakly arched, as high as compound eyes or slightly elevated in female. Pronotum slender, significantly longer than forecoxae, supracoxal dilation marked, flat-oval. Metazona many times longer than prozona, keeled; prozonal margins converging, occasionally denticulate in female, usually unarmed in male. Forecoxae with contiguous to slightly diverging apical lobes on interior surface; anteroventral margin often serrated, more so in female. Forefemora slightly dilated, dorsal margin slightly sinuate to straight, tibial spur groove placed in distal half, almost in middle. Forefemora with 4 discoidal spines and 4 posteroventral spines, between which margin is smooth to slightly serrate. Anteroventral margin with alternating large and small spines. Foretibiae with 8-11 posteroventral spines and 11-17 anteroventral spines. Meso/metathoracic legs long, exterior surface rounded. Metafemora without apical spine; basitarsi as long as or longer than other segments combined. Male forewings narrow with rounded apices, usually exceeding past abdomen, parallel. Costal area narrow to moderate in width, hyaline or opaque, irregularly reticulated. Jugal lobe hyaline or slightly gray, not darkened. Stigma often distinct, sometimes absent. Female forewings always shorter than abdomen, opaque, elliptical, apex broadly rounded, margins subparallel. Costal area typically broadened, opaque, densely reticulated. Stigma usually distinct, often colored, rounded to elongated. Male hindwings long and ample, hyaline to infumated, most often maculated with radiating rows of blotches. Female hindwings are either primarily hyaline, tessellated with colored bands, or largely iridescent-brown with hyaline venules. Variable degrees of this dichotomy is present with some species representing both characteristics. Male abdomen cylindrical, ribbon-like; female abdomen broad, slightly to strongly dilated with continuous margins. Supra-anal plate short, triangular with rounded apex, keeled, wider than long. Subgenital plate very large in male, longer than wide, apical half triangular. Cerci long, cylindrical, styli very short.

Type Species: *Gryllus carolinus* Linné, 1763 (by original designation)

The naming of the subgenera outlined below largely follows Giglio-Tos except where Rehn appropriately argued that certain species are divergent enough to constitute their own group. In these four cases, a new name for the subgenus is introduced to properly designate the referent species group established by Rehn. The diagnoses of these subgenera are as follows:

Key to Subgenera of *Stagmomantis* Males:

- 1 Anterior margin of forecoxae unarmed or with fine teeth only. Prozonal margins smooth to weakly denticulate 2
- 1' Anterior margin of forecoxae armed with thick, triangular-shaped teeth. Prozonal margins serrated *Stauromantis*

- 2 Abdominal tergites monochromatic to mottled but having no darkened bands 3
- 2' Abdominal tergites III-IV broadly edged with blackish-brown, darkening posterior third of each segment *Nigralora*

- 3 Costal area of forewings semi-opaque to wholly opaque, colored 4
- 3' Costal area of forewings entirely hyaline, clear 7

- 4 Habitus moderate to large in size or small and slender 5
- 4' Habitus small and compact *Oromantis*

- 5 Habitus moderate to large in size, elongated to robust. Costal area of forewings wholly opaque. Primarily distributed in North America 6
- 5' Habitus small to moderate in size, very slender. Costal area of forewings semi-opaque. Distributed in Central America *Uromantis*

- 6 Prothoracic legs distinctively quite slender. Pronotum with metazonal margins subparallel, supracoxal dilation slight, prozona spanning about as wide as middle of metazona *Tenuecedes*
- 6' Prothoracic legs more robust. Pronotum with metazonal margins constricted, supracoxal dilation marked, prozona spanning wider than middle of metazona
..... *Auromantis*

- 7 Metazonal margins constricted before supracoxal dilation. Prozonal margins abruptly narrowing after dilation. Body pigmentation variegated to mottled. Wings lightly to heavily maculated 8
- 7' Metazonal margins subparallel before supracoxal dilation. Prozonal margins gradually converging anteriorly, remaining equally as broad as dilation throughout most of its length. Body pigmentation monochromatic green. Wings entirely hyaline *Parviletum*

- 8 Subgenital plate stout, measuring less than 2 times as long as abdominal sternite VIII. Prozona stout, measuring 1.6-1.8 times longer than wide at middle
..... *Stagmomantis*
- 8' Subgenital plate elongated, measuring 2.5 times as long as abdominal sternite VIII. Prozona elongated, measuring 2.4 times longer than wide at middle
..... *Longicorpus*

Key to Subgenera of *Stagmomantis* Females:

- 1 Anterior margin of forecoxae unarmed or with fine teeth only. Pronotal margins smooth to denticulate 2

- 1' Anterior margin of forecoxae armed with thick, triangular-shaped teeth. Pronotal margins serrated *Stauromantis*
- 2 Abdominal tergites monochromatic to mottled but having no darkened bands 3
- 2' Abdominal tergites III-IV broadly edged with blackish-brown, darkening posterior third of each segment *Nigralora*
- 3 Metazonal margins constricted before supracoxal dilation. Prozonal margins abruptly narrowing after dilation 4
- 3' Metazonal margins subparallel before supracoxal dilation. Prozonal margins gradually converging anteriorly, remaining equally as broad as dilation throughout most of its length *Parviletum*
- 4 Forewing length surpassing abdominal tergite III 6
- 4' Forewing length not reaching distal margin of abdominal tergite III 5
- 5 Habitus of large size, elongate-slender. Endemic to Florida *Longicorpus*
- 5' Habitus small and compact. Distributed from tropical Mexico to Central America *Oromantis*
- 6 Habitus elongated and slender 7
- 6' Habitus stocky and robust 8
- 7 Metazonal margins constricted before supracoxal dilation. Abdomen strongly fusiform, margins broadly widened in middle. Distributed in Central America *Uromantis*
- 7' Metazonal margins subparallel before supracoxal dilation. Abdomen subfusiform, margins nearly equal in width throughout to slightly widened. Distributed in Arizona and northern Mexico *Tenuecedes*
- 8 Costal area of forewings wide, spanning at least one-third that of discoidal area ...
..... *Auromantis*
- 8' Costal area of forewings narrow, spanning much less than one-third that of discoidal area *Stagmomantis*

Stagmomantis (Auromantis) Giglio-Tos, 1917 **stat. rev.**

Diagnosis. Habitus moderate to large in size. Males with wings lightly to heavily maculated, costal area of forewings wholly opaque, colored. Females with forewing length surpassing abdominal tergite III, costal area wide, spanning at least one-third that of discoidal area. Abdomen strongly fusiform, margins broadly widened in middle. Both sexes with anterior margin of forecoxae armed with fine teeth. Pronotal margins smooth to sparsely denticulate. Supracoxal dilation marked. Metazonal margins constricted before dilation. Prozona spanning wider than middle of metazona. margins abruptly narrowing after dilation. Abdominal tergites monochromatic to mottled but having no

darkened bands. Body pigmentation variegated to mottled. Distributed from United States to Central America.

Type Species. *Mantis limbata* Hahn, 1835

Species Checklist:

- *Stagmomantis (Auromantis) limbata* (Hahn, 1835)
- *Stagmomantis (Auromantis) montana* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894
- *Stagmomantis (Auromantis) montana sinaloae* Rehn, 1935

Taxonomy Note. Giglio-Tos erected *Auromantis* as a genus to include those species that have males with opaque costal areas of their forewings and corresponding females that have forewing costal areas spanning more than one-third that of the discoidal area. In 1927, included in this genus by Giglio-Tos were: *cinctipes* Giglio-Tos, 1917, *androgyna* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894, *gracilipes* Rehn, 1907, *montana* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894 and *limbata* Hahn, 1835. Rehn synonymized both *androgyna* and *cinctipes* with *montana* in 1935 and created the “Limbata Group,” which is closely aligned with *Auromantis*, to include the two remaining species, *montana* and *limbata*. He deselected *gracilipes* away from the subdivision at this time and moved this species into its own group.

Stagmomantis (Longicorpus) n. subgen.

Diagnosis. Habitus large in size, elongated. Males with wings immaculate to lightly maculated, costal area of forewings entirely hyaline, clear. Subgenital plate elongated, measuring 2.5 times as long as abdominal sternite VIII. Females with forewing length not reaching distal margin of abdominal tergite III, costal area of forewings narrow, spanning much less than one-third that of discoidal area. Abdomen subcylindrical to subfusiform, margins nearly equal in width throughout to slightly widened. Supra-anal plate broadly rounded. Both sexes with anterior margin of forecoxae armed with fine teeth. Pronotal margins unarmed, smooth. Supracoxal dilation marked. Metazonal margins constricted before dilation. Prozona elongated, measuring 2.4 times longer than wide at middle, margins abruptly narrowing after dilation. Abdominal tergites monochromatic. Body pigmentation variegated to mottled. Endemic to Florida.

Type Species. *Stagmomantis floridensis* Davis, 1919

Species Checklist:

- *Stagmomantis (Longicorpus) floridensis* Davis, 1919

Taxonomy Note. Rehn placed *floridensis* Davis, 1919 into its own “Floridensis Group” in 1935. This species was not addressed by Giglio-Tos in 1917, as it had not yet been described at that time. Although Giglio-Tos’ 1927 monograph of world Mantodea was published eight years after Davis’ description of *floridensis*, this species was not addressed within that volume because it was, per Giglio-Tos, “not mentioned in the work from 1921 until 1927” within the compiled references used by him to generate the monograph. This subgenus contains just one species, *floridensis*, which has been treated at length in 2019 by Anderson.

Etymology. *Longicorpus* is a Latin derivative for “long body,” referencing the larger, elongated habitus of its type species in comparison to its Nearctic congeners.

Stagmomantis (Nigralora) n. subgen.

Diagnosis. Habitus moderate in size. Males with wings heavily maculated, costal area of forewings wholly opaque, colored. Females with forewing length surpassing abdominal tergite III, costal area of forewings narrow, spanning less than one-third that of discoidal area. Abdomen fusiform, margins broadly widened in middle. Both sexes with anterior margin of forecoxae armed with fine teeth. Pronotal margins smooth to sparsely denticulate. Supracoxal dilation marked. Metazonal margins constricted before dilation. Prozona margins abruptly narrowing after dilation. Abdominal tergites III-IV broadly edged with blackish-brown, darkening posterior third of each segment. Body pigmentation variegated to mottled. Distributed from United States to Mexico.

Type Species. *Stagmomantis wheelerii* Thomas, 1875

Species Checklist:

- *Stagmomantis (Nigralora) colorata* Hebard, 1922
- *Stagmomantis (Nigralora) wheelerii* (Thomas, 1875)

Taxonomy Note. Rehn created the “Californica Group” in 1935 to include *californica* Rehn & Hebard, 1909 and *colorata* Hebard, 1922. He noted: “the California Group has distinctive male genital features (i.e. of both dorsal and ventral sinistral valves and of the apex of the ultimate sternite), as well as very definite color peculiarities of abdomen, tegmina and wings in its brown phase individuals.” Giglio-Tos originally placed *californica* within *Uromantis*, one of his newly erected genera. He did not address *colorata* in 1917, as it had not yet been described. This species was likewise not included by Giglio-Tos in 1927, as it was another that was not listed within the compiled references used to generate his monograph. Giglio-Tos listed *wheelerii* Thomas, 1875 in his 1927 work but noted that this species was “known only by the insufficient description given by Thomas,” whereas *wheelerii* was considered a synonym of *carolina* by Rehn during this time. This subgenus contains just *colorata* and *wheelerii*, as *californica* has been synonymized with the latter by Anderson in 2018. This subgenus will likely be elevated to the rank of genus, given the distinctive genitalia and maculation differences noted by Rehn. Additionally, preliminary results from the phylogenetic study conducted by Rodrigues in 2018 concerning *Stagmomantis* and related genera have reportedly found that *colorata* could be more closely related to *Phasmomantis* Saussure, 1869 than to other *Stagmomantis* species.

Etymology. *Nigralora* is a Latin derivative for “black straps” or “black reins,” referencing the black-margined abdominal tergites that are found within members of this subgenus and no other species of *Stagmomantis*.

Stagmomantis (Oromantis) Giglio-Tos, 1917 **stat. rev.**

Diagnosis. Habitus small in size, compact. Males with wings lightly to heavily maculated, costal area of forewings semi-opaque, colored. Females with forewing length not reaching distal margin of abdominal tergite III, costal area moderately widened, spanning approximately one-third that of discoidal area. Abdomen subparallel to fusiform, margins narrowly widened in middle. Both sexes with anterior margin of forecoxae armed with fine teeth. Pronotal margins smooth to sparsely denticulate. Supracoxal dilation marked. Metazonal margins constricted before dilation. Prozona

margins abruptly narrowing after dilation. Abdominal tergites monochromatic. Body pigmentation monochromatic to variegated. Distributed from tropical Mexico to Central America.

Type Species. *Stagmomantis nahua* Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist:

- *Stagmomantis (Oromantis) nahua* Saussure, 1869
- *Stagmomantis (Oromantis) vicina* Saussure, 1870

Taxonomy Note. Giglio-Tos erected *Oromantis* as a genus to include those species that have a combination of morphological characters that include a small body size, divergent coxal lobes, and males with hyaline costal areas of their forewings with corresponding females that have forewing length not reaching distal margin of abdominal tergite III. In 1927, included in this genus by Giglio-Tos were *nahua* Saussure, 1869 and *vicina* Saussure, 1870. In 1935, Rehn created the “Nahua Group” to likewise include these same two species and added *centralis* Giglio-Tos, 1917 into this subdivision, which Giglio-Tos had originally included under *Uromantis* based solely on the opaque costal area of the male forewings, a character that Rehn found to be variable. At present, *centralis* has been returned to *Uromantis*, as Giglio-Tos originally formulated this grouping, due to having a much slenderer habitus that more closely aligns with *heterogamia* and *venusta* than it does with the more compact and smaller body plan of *Oromantis*.

Stagmomantis (Parviletum) n. subgen.

Diagnosis. Habitus small in size, compact. Males with wings hyaline, costal area of forewings entirely hyaline, clear. Females with forewing length surpassing abdominal tergite III, costal area wide, spanning at least one-third that of discoidal area. Abdomen fusiform, margins widened in middle. Both sexes with anterior margin of forecoxae nearly smooth, armed with very small teeth. Pronotal margins smooth to finely denticulate. Supracoxal dilation marked. Metazonal margins subparallel before supracoxal dilation. Prozonal margins gradually converging anteriorly, remaining equally as broad as dilation throughout most of its length. Abdominal tergites monochromatic. Body pigmentation monochromatic green. Distributed from tropical Mexico to Central America.

Type Species. *Stagmomantis fraterna* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894

Species Checklist:

- *Stagmomantis (Parviletum) fraterna* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894

Taxonomy Note. In 1935, Rehn created the “Fraterna Group” to include a single species, *fraterna* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894. Within his treatment of Central American *Stagmomantis* he noted: “The Fraterna Group, made up solely of *fraterna*, is puzzling, showing as it does certain tendencies, as the bisinuate transverse ultimate tergite of the female, the slightly convex margin of the ultimate sternite in the male, and the shape of the head and pronotum, which are shared to a marked degree with other groups, but in the broad and depressed, cultriform yet apically spiniform ventral sinistral genital valve of the male it is distinctive and unique, the only suggestion of this elsewhere in the genus being the faintest possible one in the otherwise very different Gracilipes Group.” Giglio-

Tos originally placed *fraterna* within *Stagmomantis* proper, along with *maya* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894, which was later synonymized with *fraterna* by Ehrmann in 2002.

Etymology. *Parviletum* is a Latin derivative for “small doom,” referencing the diminutive size of its type species in comparison to its congeners.

Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) Saussure, 1869

Diagnosis. Habitus small to moderate in size. Males with wings lightly to heavily maculated, costal area of forewings entirely hyaline, clear. Subgenital plate stout, measuring less than 2 times as long as abdominal sternite VIII. Females with forewing length surpassing abdominal tergite III, costal area of forewings narrow, spanning less than one-third that of discoidal area. Abdomen subfusiform to strongly fusiform. Both sexes with anterior margin of forecoxae armed with fine teeth. Pronotal margins smooth to sparsely denticulate. Supracoxal dilation slight to marked. Metazonal margins constricted before dilation. Prozona stout, measuring 1.6-1.8 times longer than wide at middle. Abdominal tergites monochromatic to mottled but having no darkened bands. Body pigmentation variegated to mottled. Distributed from United States to northern South America.

Type Species. *Gryllus carolinus* Linné, 1763

Species Checklist:

- *Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) carolina* (Linné, 1763)
- *Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) coerulans* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894
- *Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) conspurcata* (Serville, 1839)
- *Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) hebaridi* Rehn, 1935

Taxonomy Note. Giglio-Tos demarcated this core genus to retain the several species that are closely allied to *carolina* Linné, 1763. The species included by Giglio-Tos within this genus were: *coerulans* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894, *latipennis* Burmeister, 1838, *nordica* Giglio-Tos, 1917, *simplex* Giglio-Tos, 1917, *inquinata* Serville, 1839, *ferox* Saussure, 1859, *polita* Giglio-Tos, 1917, *stollii* Saussure, 1869, *dimidiata* Burmeister, 1838, *conspersa* Burmeister, 1838, *fraterna* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894, and *maya* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894. Rehn referred to his parallel subdivision of these species as the “Carolina Group” but only included one species, *hebaridi* Rehn, 1935, to accompany *carolina*. With the exceptions of *conspersa*, which was determined to belong to *Coptopteryx*, and the aforementioned *fraterna* and *maya* that were deselected into a separate group, all of the other species originally listed by Giglio-Tos within this subdivision were subsequently synonymized under *carolina*. This historic synonymization confounded several legitimate species and resulted in *carolina* turning into a taxonomic dumping ground for many decades. Currently, this subgenus contains the two species placed by Rehn, *carolina* and *hebaridi*, in addition to *coerulans* that had been originally listed in this subdivision by Giglio-Tos. One previously synonymized species, *conspurcata* Serville, 1839, is believed to be valid. The argument for reinstatement of *conspurcata* is included hereafter.

Stagmomantis (Stauromantis) Giglio-Tos, 1917 **stat. rev.**

Diagnosis. Habitus moderate in size. Males with wings immaculate to lightly maculated, costal area of forewings semi-opaque, colored. Females with forewing length surpassing abdominal tergite III, costal area of forewings wide, spanning at least one-third that of discoidal area. Abdomen fusiform, margins widened in middle. Both sexes with anterior margin of forecoxae armed with thick, triangular-shaped teeth. Prozonal margins serrated, extending into metazona in female. Supracoxal dilation marked. Metazonal margins constricted before dilation. Prozona margins abruptly narrowing after dilation. Abdominal tergites monochromatic. Body pigmentation monochromatic green. Distributed from Central America to northern South America.

Type Species. *Stagmomantis theophila* Rehn, 1904

Species Checklist:

- *Stagmomantis (Stauromantis) theophila* Rehn, 1904

Taxonomy Note. Giglio-Tos erected *Stauromantis* as a genus to include those species that have distinctly serrated pronotal margins and triangular-shaped denticulation along the anterior margin of the forecoxae. In 1927, included in this genus by Giglio-Tos were: *pagana* Saussure, 1870, *theophila* Rehn, 1904 and *festae* Giglio-Tos, 1917. All three names were later determined to represent the same species. In 1935, Rehn created the “Theophila Group,” which is closely aligned with *Stauromantis*, to include just *theophila*. This subgenus will very likely be reinstated as a valid genus in the near future, given its distinctive morphology and marked differences in the male genitalia apart from other members of *Stagmomantis*.

Stagmomantis (Tenuecedes) **n. subgen.**

Diagnosis. Habitus moderate in size. Males with wings lightly maculated, costal area of forewings wholly opaque, colored. Females with forewing length surpassing abdominal tergite III, costal area of forewings narrow, spanning less than one-third that of discoidal area. Abdomen subcylindrical to subfusiform, margins nearly equal in width throughout to slightly widened. Supra-anal plate narrowly triangular. Both sexes with prothoracic legs distinctively quite slender, anterior margin of forecoxae armed with fine teeth. Pronotal margins smooth to sparsely denticulate. Supracoxal dilation marked. Pronotum with metazonal margins subparallel, supracoxal expansion slight, prozona spanning about as wide as middle of metazona. Abdominal tergites monochromatic. Body pigmentation variegated. Distributed from Arizona to northern Mexico.

Type Species. *Stagmomantis gracilipes* Rehn, 1907

Species Checklist:

- *Stagmomantis (Tenuecedes) gracilipes* Rehn, 1907

Taxonomy Note. In 1935, Rehn created the “Gracilipes Group” to include a single species, *gracilipes* Rehn, 1907. Within his treatment of Central American *Stagmomantis* he noted: “The Gracilipes Group has in its single species a readily recognized combination of features, of which the triangularly produced ultimate tergite (supra-anal plate) of the female is found in no other *Stagmomantis*.” Giglio-Tos originally placed *gracilipes* within *Auromantis* due to the males exhibiting an opaque costal margin of the forewings, a character that Rehn pointed out was not altogether diagnostic. Currently,

this subgenus continues to contain just *gracilipes*, which was treated at length by Anderson in 2019.

Etymology. *Tenuecedes* is a Latin derivative for “thin death,” referencing the slender habitus of this uncommon species.

Stagmomantis (Uromantis) Giglio-Tos, 1917 **stat. rev.**

Diagnosis. Habitus small to moderate in size, very slender. Males with wings moderately maculated, costal area of forewings semi-opaque, colored. Females with forewing length surpassing abdominal tergite III, costal area wide, spanning at least one-third that of discoidal area. Abdomen fusiform, margins widened in middle. Both sexes with anterior margin of forecoxae armed with fine teeth. Pronotal margins smooth to sparsely denticulate. Supracoxal dilation marked. Metazonal margins constricted before dilation. Prozona margins abruptly narrowing after dilation. Abdominal tergites monochromatic. Body pigmentation monochromatic to variegated. Distributed in Central America.

Type Species. *Stagmomantis venusta* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894

Species Checklist:

- *Stagmomantis (Uromantis) centralis* (Giglio-Tos, 1917)
- *Stagmomantis (Uromantis) heterogamia* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894
- *Stagmomantis (Uromantis) parvidentata* Beier, 1931
- *Stagmomantis (Uromantis) venusta* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894

Taxonomy Note. Giglio-Tos erected *Uromantis* as a genus to include those species that have a combination of morphological characters that include a small body stature, divergent coxal lobes, males with opaque costal areas of their forewings and corresponding females that have forewing length surpassing abdominal tergite III. In 1927, included in this genus by Giglio-Tos were *heterogamia* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894, *venusta* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894, *californica* Rehn & Hebard, 1909, *centralis* Giglio-Tos, 1917, and *similis* Giglio-Tos, 1917. In 1935, Rehn created the “Heterogamia Group,” which is closely aligned with *Uromantis*, to include *heterogamia*, *venusta*, and *parvidentata* Beier, 1931. As previously noted, Rehn moved *californica* into the Californica Group and *centralis*, which he synonymized with *similis*, into his Nahua Group.

References. Burmeister (1838) pg 539; Guérin-Méneville (1857) pg 348; Saussure (1869) pg 56; Saussure (1871) pgs 48-50; Saussure (1872) pgs 242-243; Stal (1877) pg 39; Cockerell (1894) pg 258; Saussure & Zehntner (1894) pg 139; Rehn (1903) pg 131; Rehn (1904) pgs 564-565; Rehn (1911) pg 11; Giglio-Tos (1917) pgs 53-57; Blatchley (1920) pgs 117-118; Hebard (1922) pg 339; Werner (1925) pgs 160-163; Giglio-Tos (1927) pgs 378-379, 385, 387; Beier (1935) pg 94; Rehn (1935) pgs 218-240; Terra (1995) pg 57; Ehrmann (2002) pg 330; Maxwell (2014) pgs 501-526; Anderson (2018) pgs 158-162; Rodrigues (2019) pers. comm.

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